

From Automation to Autonomous: Driving the Optical Network Management to Fixed Fifth-generation (F5G) Advanced

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Abstract— An autonomous optical network operates with little or no human involvement and has the capability to configure, oversee, and sustain itself without external intervention. This paper presents the latest advances of autonomous networking (AN) proposed in TM Forum for optical networks. Each step in the procedure for the operator’s daily work is mapped into the AN framework, with detailed features specified in each level. The solution is based on a standard architecture and data models specified in IETF, known as *Abstraction and Control of Traffic Engineering Networks* (ACTN). Use cases are presented and conducted. This paper presents the result in three typical use cases for optical network management and maintenances: optical service provisioning, healthy assurance, and intelligent alarm processing. **Keywords** — *Autonomous Networking, Capability Level, Standard Interfaces*

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) have become increasingly prevalent in network operator environments. By providing advanced automation capabilities, these technologies have facilitated significant improvements in network planning, construction, maintenance, optimization, and other areas.

The development of optical networks has been greatly accelerated by SDN technologies. As a result, the optical transport network is now much closer to the end-user, thanks to leased line service, slices and other kind of services. The range of available services has also become more diverse with the emergence of applications such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). SDN provides end-to-end network management capabilities, allowing for timely feedback to the users to improve their satisfaction.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) are valuable methodologies for enhancing the effectiveness of the SDN functionalities. When applied to optical networks, AI/ML can offer several benefits. Self-configuration technology, for instance, allows for automatic management of network devices and service

provisioning, ensuring uninterrupted service upgrades. Self-healing technology enables fast network fault identification, accurate diagnosis and location, and self-healing without affecting user and operations and maintenance (O&M) experience. Additionally, self-optimization technology can optimize resource configurations based on specific scenarios, resulting in more efficient network resource utilization.

The challenges associated with implementing AI/ML in optical networks have also been proposed. While algorithms can be applied to enhance explicit operation functionalities, their complexity should be evaluated to avoid causing unnecessary delays. Algorithms that are too complicated or time-consuming may impact the timeliness of response and cause unnecessary delay in the overall procedure. Additionally, there is a concern regarding the additional computation and storage resource requirements in the network. Ensuring the accuracy of AI/ML algorithms is also crucial, as any unexpected event/failure could impact the operation procedure.

The ETSI ISG Fifth Generation Fixed Network (F5G) initiative has a clear objective of establishing a systematic approach to the development of fixed networks. This will be achieved by creating a roadmap for generational planning and promoting the expansion of technology to various sectors through Fibre-To-The-Everywhere-and-Everything (FTTE). F5G Advanced is focused on nine key applications or industries, which can be broadly categorized into two groups: those that are service and application-oriented, and those that are geared towards network transformation. Autonomous Networking (AN) has been proposed in TM Forum since 2020 and iterates a few rounds afterwards [1]. The procedure of operations is decomposed into 5 steps include the execution, awareness, analysis, decision and intent. The automation of each step is marked as ‘completed by people (manual)’ or ‘completed by system (autonomous)’. Six levels of autonomous were introduced based on such classification, as shown in Fig. 1.

Autonomous Levels	L0: Manual Operation & Maintenance	L1: Assisted Operation & Maintenance	L2: Partial Autonomous Networks	L3: Conditional Autonomous Networks	L4: High Autonomous Networks	L5: Full Autonomous Networks
Execution	P	P/S	S	S	S	S
Awareness	P	P/S	P/S	S	S	S
Analysis	P	P	P/S	P/S	S	S
Decision	P	P	P	P/S	S	S
Intent/ Experience	P	P	P	P	P/S	S
Applicability	N/A	Select scenarios				All scenarios

P: People (manual) S: System (autonomous)

Fig. 1. Generic Criteria for Autonomous Level Classification (TM Forum)

This paper is targeting the latest application of autonomous networking, which can reach a Level of 3.5. It means 50% of the procedure reached Level 3 and the rest 50% reached L4. Section 2 describes the use cases for optical network operation and maintenances, including the service provisioning as well as the intelligent alarm processing and the healthy assurance for transport services. Section 3 presents the supporting technologies, including architecture, interface and the correspondent standard. Section 4 summarizes this paper.

II. FRAMEWORK FOR AUTONOMOUS NETWORKS

Autonomous networking is an emerging field in the world of computer networking that promises to revolutionize the way we manage and operate networks. At the heart of this paradigm is intent management, a framework that allows operators and users to specify their desired outcomes in terms of high-level goals and objectives, rather than low-level details such as configuration settings.

The intent management will sit on top of four pillars that interact to provide network automation: awareness, analysis, decision, and execution, as shown in Fig 2. The first pillar, *awareness*, refers to the ability of the system to gather data from various sources, such as network devices, applications, and user behaviour, and to use this information to build a comprehensive picture of the network status and environment.

The second pillar, *analysis*, involves the use of advanced algorithms and machine learning techniques to extract insights from the data gathered in the awareness phase. This analysis can be used to identify patterns and trends, predict future behaviour, and detect anomalies and potential issues.

The third pillar, *decision*, involves the use of these insights to make informed decisions about how to best achieve the desired outcomes specified in the intent. These decisions may involve adjusting network configurations, rerouting traffic, or even launching new services or applications.

Finally, the fourth pillar, *execution*, involves the implementation of these decisions in an automated and orchestrated manner, without the need for human intervention. This can include the deployment of new network resources, the configuration of devices, or the optimization of network traffic.

Overall, the framework for autonomous network provides a powerful and flexible approach to network management that enables operators and users to focus on the outcomes they want to achieve, rather than the details of how those outcomes are achieved. By incorporating awareness, analysis, decision, and execution, autonomous networking systems can adapt to changing network conditions and user needs, providing a more efficient, resilient, and scalable network infrastructure.

Fig. 2. Proposed framework for autonomous networks

III. AUTONOMOUS NETWORK USE CASES

Optical Service Provisioning, Healthy Assurance, and Intelligent Alarm Processing are three emerging autonomous network use cases. Optical Service Provisioning is used to configure and activate high-speed optical network services, enabling telecom providers to quickly and easily provision services to meet the needs of their customers. Healthy Assurance uses advanced analytics and AI to monitor and manage the health of network systems. Intelligent Alarm Processing uses machine learning and AI to analyze and respond to alarms generated by various network systems and devices, improving operational efficiency and reducing the risk of downtime. These three use cases demonstrate the power of autonomous networks.

A. Optical Service Provisioning

In the optical leased line scenario, the service is expected to be automatically provisioned. The goal of network service provisioning is to shorten the service provisioning time and reduce complaints.

The workflow of service provisioning could be decomposed into provisioning process scheduling, resource survey, resource adjustment, and service delivery/test. The four subtasks can be mapped to the general workflow of network management, control, and operation, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Mapping sub-task into AN framework – Service Provisioning

Provisioning process scheduling could be mapped to the intent management and awareness in the AN framework, including service workflow scheduling and change process scheduling according to special event such as migration. In this step, it would be greatly useful for path computation if the network parameters could be detected timely, accurately, and automatically. Such parameters may include the network resource status (link/port), bandwidth and latency.

Resource survey could be mapped to the analysis in the AN framework. The survey is done per users' service requirements and real-time network status. Based on the survey result, the operator can design the solution and conduct corresponding simulations to validate the provisioning.

When there are multiple designs for one special service demand, the selection of solutions designed for resource adjustment and path computation could be mapped into the decision in the AN framework. The objective is to choose the optimal solution from these designs and produce how to adjust the resources.

The service delivery could be mapped into the execution in the AN framework, which is the final step of the service provisioning. After that the service should be verified via testing tools and the result should be confirmed, to guarantee the service connectivity and SLA meet requirements.

The level of AN for service provisioning could be evaluated based on the criteria in Fig. 1. The test result in a CCSA event provides the following capabilities, as shown in Table I. Please noted the test of this and the following use cases are only focusing on the vendor side which covers the awareness, analysis, decision and execution. The intent management is more operator and users involved and is therefore skipped in this test event. A final result of average 3.5 is obtained through contributions of Awareness (4), Analysis (3), Decision (4) and Execution (3).

TABLE I. LEVEL EVALUATION FOR SERVICE PROVISIONING

AN Procedure	UC Mapping	Test Score	Average
Intent Management	Provisioning Process	N/A	3.5
Awareness	Scheduling	4	
Analysis	Resource Survey	3	
Decision	Resource Adjustment	4	
Execution	Service Delivery & Verification	3	

B. Healthy Assurance

Healthy assurance starts after network construction and service provisioning. The objective is to accurately detect and rectify faults in a timely manner. The specific technical aspects are to improve the user experience and reduce the O&M cost. AI/ML technology is especially useful in recent years since these technologies provide the capability to predict what may happen in the near future.

Fig. 4. Mapping sub-task into AN framework – Healthy Assurance

The workflow of healthy assurance could be decomposed into customized monitoring, risk identification, diagnosis, impact analysis, troubleshooting solution, and service

verification. These subtasks can be mapped to the general workflow of network management, control, and operation as shown in Fig. 4. The healthy assurance starts from the monitoring requirement as the intent management. Customized monitoring requirement could be created by choosing explicit parameters according to the intent requirements, as well as the creation of monitoring points and telemetry sources/streams

The risk identification can be mapped to the *awareness* in the AN framework. Risks in the network include ‘what happened in the network’ (known as failure and indicated by alarm) and ‘what may happen and damage the network’ (known as potential risk and predicted by AI/ML algorithm). Such analysis could be done based on the parameters collected in the management system, in order to recognize the risks that may cause failure in the future.

Diagnosis and impact analysis can be mapped to the analysis module in the AN framework. According to the risk detected, the diagnosis is responsible for accurately locating the problem, which may include the geographical information of the fibre, the explicit optical module or board, with the exact problems to be solved. Impact analysis provides the evaluation of the failure or potential risk, to help produce the solution.

The troubleshooting solutions are provided in the decision step, based on the recognized failure or risk. Detailed design on recovery or adjustment is generated to solve the problem detected.

The solution is then conducted as the execution in the AN procedure. The failure and/or risks are expected to disappear after solving the problem. Service verification will be applied to guarantee the issue is closed and the network/services are recovered.

The level of AN for service provisioning could be evaluated based on the criteria in Fig. 1. The test result in a CCSA event provides the following capabilities, as shown in Table II. A final result of average 3.5 is obtained through contributions of Awareness (4), Analysis (3), Decision (3) and Execution (4).

TABLE II. LEVEL EVALUATION FOR HEALTHY ASSURANCE

AN Procedure	UC Mapping	Test Score	Average
Intent Management	Customized monitor	N/A	3.5
Awareness	Risk Identification	4	
Analysis	Impact Analysis	3	
Decision	Troubleshooting	3	
Execution	Service Verification	4	

C. Intelligent Alarm Processing

Alarms are automatically generated when the network element or system detects a failure. Given the massive connections/services in the optical transport network, one fibre cut failure will cause the interruption of thousands of services in the network. Therefore, there is a huge number of concurrent alarms in the system and it is quite challenging to figure out the root cause. The objective for intelligent alarm is to apply the AI/ML algorithm to recognize the most likely root cause and therefore drastically reduce the number of alarms.

The workflow of intelligent alarm processing could be decomposed into: alarm collection and pre-processing,

diagnosis and impact analysis, solution generation, processing and service verification. These seven subtasks can be mapped to the general workflow of network management, control, and operation as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Mapping sub-task into AN framework – Intelligent alarm Processing

The alarm collection and pre-processing can be mapped to the awareness in the AN framework. Since massive alarm needs to be collected, the pre-processing is also required to remove the redundant alarm and normalized the alarm for the diagnosis and analysis in the next step.

Diagnosis and impact analysis can be mapped to the analysis in the AN framework. According to the risk detected, the diagnosis is responsible for accurately locating the problem, which may include the geographical information of the fibre, the explicit optical module or board, with the exact problems to be solved. Impact analysis provides the evaluation of the failure or potential risk, to help produce the solution.

The troubleshooting solutions are provided in the decision step, based on the recognized failure or risk. Detailed design on recovery or adjustment is generated to solve the problem detected.

The solution is then conducted as the execution in the AN procedure. The failure and/or risks are expected to disappear after solving the problem. Service verification will be applied to guarantee closing the problem.

The level of AN for service provisioning could be evaluated based on the criteria in Fig. 1. The test result in a CCSA event provides the following capabilities, as shown in Table III. A final result of average 3.5 is obtained through contributions of Awareness (4), Analysis (4), Decision (3) and Execution (3).

TABLE III. LEVEL EVALUATION FOR INTELLIGENT ALARM PROCESSING

AN Procedure	UC Mapping	Test Score	Average
Intent Management	Customized Alarm	N/A	3.5
Awareness	Collect & Pre-process	4	
Analysis	Impact Analysis	4	
Decision	Generate Solution	3	
Execution	Processing & Verification	3	

IV. SUPPORTING TECHNOLOGIES AND STANDARD

The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) is developing the architecture and a set of standard YANG models which are applicable to these AN use cases.

Abstraction and Control of Traffic Engineering (TE) Networks (ACTN) is a framework, defined in [2], that enables the control of multi-layer/multi-domain networks.

The ACTN framework provides a hierarchical control architecture, shown in Fig. 2, that decouples the mechanisms being used for intra-domain control (such as MPLS-TE, ASON/GMPLS, PCEP, static configuration or even vendor-specific mechanisms) from the mechanisms being used for multi-domain control.

Fig. 6. ACTN Base Architecture

The Multi-Domain Service Coordinator (MDSC) is responsible for multi-domain coordination among different Provisioning Network Controllers (PNCs) which are responsible for intra-domain control.

The different domains controlled by the MDSC can be different technology domains (e.g., packet network or optical network domains) or different optical vendor domains. As such ACTN can be used for automatic control of Packet/Optical Integrated (POI) networks, as outlined in [3], as well as of multi-vendor optical networks, as outlined in [4].

A well-defined common open MDSC-PNC Interface (MPI) between the MDSC and each PNCs is required to control multi-vendor and multi-domain networks and also enable coordination and automation of service provisioning. This is facilitated by using standardized data models (e.g., YANG models), and an appropriate protocol (e.g., RESTCONF [5]).

A couple of data models have also been standardized as YANG in IETF. They are based on common, technology-agnostic, TE Topology, TE Tunnel and Path Computation models, defined in [6], [7] and [8], with different technology-specific augmentations models for: Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) networks, as defined in [9], [10], [11], [12], [13] and [14]; Optical Transport Network (OTN) networks, as defined in [15], [16] and [17]; Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS) TE (MPLS-TE), including MPLS Transport Profile (MPLS-TP), networks, as defined in [18] and [19]; and Ethernet networks, as defined in [20].

The models for transparent and Ethernet services provided by transport networks, e.g., OTN, are defined in [21] while the models for the Layer 2 Virtual Private Network (L2VPN) and Layer 3 VPN (L3VPN) services provided by packet networks are defined in [22] and [23].

Although in the original framework in [2], the MDSC was intended to provide services directly to the customer, in current real network deployments the MDSC is providing services to a higher-level Operations Support System (OSS)/Orchestration layer.

[24] proposes YANG data models that describe performance monitoring parameters and scaling intent mechanisms for TE-tunnels and Virtual Networks (VNs). These performance monitoring parameters are exposed as the key telemetry data for tunnels and VN. These models can be utilized by a client network controller to initiate the capabilities via a NETCONF or a RESTCONF interface and use the acquired data in Awareness phase.

As outlined in [24] and [25], by interfacing with a higher-level OSS/Orchestration layer, the MDCS can provide support for the realization of the IETF network slicing, defined in [26], and the OTN network slicing, defined in [25]. IETF and OTN network slicing enables the support of new enhanced services such as 5G transport slicing, network wholesale services, network infrastructure sharing among operators, NFV connectivity and Data Center Interconnect (DCI).

The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) is developing a set of standard YANG models which are applicable at the interface toward a higher-level Orchestration layer to support the new services. The model for the IETF network slicing is defined in [27] [28] while the models for OTN network slicing are defined in [26].

V. SUMMARY

This paper presents some recent work on the level of intelligence measurement for network management. A few mature cases already have been presented, including optical service provisioning, healthy assurance, and intelligent alarm processing.

The industrial expectation is to achieve a general level of L3 in 2023, with the further objective to achieve L4 in 2025. This work is also aligned with the pace of F5G and advanced. The ETSI F5G ISG also kicked off the level capability specification and evaluation methodology by accepting the new work item 0019. The specification will be produced for a complete level with a comprehensive evaluation method.

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